

A “simple” problem that doctors of science cannot solve. In a popular science presentation

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Annotation. This is shocking. Hundreds of students, engineers with higher education, candidates and even doctors of science cannot solve the simplest problem that is understandable to any schoolchild. This is the task. Andrey and Vladimir with their watches are moving towards each other. According to one clock, 100 seconds pass before the meeting. How many seconds will pass before the meeting according to the other clock? From the article you will learn why doctors of science are not able to solve this “simple” problem. You will learn how to solve this problem correctly.

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Introduction

We present to the reader a simple-looking problem about a moving clock, which is a “tough nut to crack” even for candidates and doctors of science. Not one of the hundreds of university students, engineers with higher education, candidates and doctors of physical, mathematical and technical sciences who tried to solve this problem was able to solve it. The task is simple: two clocks are moving towards each other. The time that will pass until the clocks meet one clock at a time is known. You need to find the time that will pass before the meeting using another clock. It would seem that it is possible to come up with a simpler task? More complex problems are published in the popular scientific and mathematical journal “Kvant” for schoolchildren.

Fig. 1. 100 seconds before the meeting between Andrei and Vladimir

So, the task is formulated for schoolchildren. Andrei and Vladimir are moving towards each other along the road. They have a clock (Fig. 1). According to one clock, 100 seconds will pass before the meeting. How long will it be before the meeting according to other hours? Any schoolchild will answer: according to other clocks, exactly the same amount of time will pass, 100 seconds.

However, this task is challenging for PhDs. The fact is that, in accordance with SRT (special theory of relativity), the passage of time of clocks moving relative to each other depends on the speed of movement. This effect in STR is called “relativistic time dilation”. The essence of this effect is simple to understand: moving clocks go slower than stationary ones. Therefore, if 100 seconds pass according to the readings of a stationary clock, then less time will pass according to the moving clock. How much less? According to SRT, the deceleration of a clock depends on the speed of movement. The faster the clock moves, the slower it goes. At half the speed of light (the speed of light is approximately 300,000,000 meters per second), a moving

clock runs approximately 1.15 times slower than a stationary clock. At a speed of movement equal to 0.866 times the speed of light, a moving clock runs approximately 2 times slower than a stationary clock.

The general formula is [1, p.19 ; 2, p. 22]:

$$\text{Moving clock time} = \text{Stationary clock time} \times \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\text{Speed}}{\text{Speed of light}}\right)^2} \text{ seconds.}$$

If, for example, 100 seconds pass according to a stationary clock, and the “Speed” of movement is 0.866 times the speed of light, then

$$\text{Moving clock time} = 100 \times \sqrt{1 - 0,866^2} = 50 \text{ seconds.}$$

While 100 seconds will pass according to a stationary clock, only 50 seconds will pass according to a moving clock, that is, 2 times less.

Let us now formulate the problem taking into account the effects of SRT.

Task

Let two rows of clocks move relative to each other in deep space (Fig. 2). Each row of watches is rigidly attached to long, solid, for example, metal rods that move parallel to each other in close proximity.

The clocks in each row are synchronized with each other. At the moment of time “00:00:00” (the beginning of the next day), according to the synchronized clocks of one row, the clocks of the other row are also set to “00:00:00” according to the readings of the clocks of the opposite row closest to them. At this point in time, all clocks in both series are synchronized.

Fig. 2. The problem of clocks moving towards each other.

Near the clock *A*, located in the first row, there is an observer *A*. Near the clock *B*, located in the second row, there is an observer *B*. From the point of view of observer *A*, clock *A* and all other clocks in the first row are stationary, while clock *B* and all other clocks in the second row are moving. From the point of view of observer *B*, clock *B* and all other clocks in the second row are stationary, while clock *A* and all other clocks in the first row are moving.

The speed of relative motion of the rows is 0.866 times the speed of light.

Clock *A* in the front row and clock *B* in the second row they are equipped with proximity sensors, for example hypothetical limit switches that are triggered when these watches approach (pass each other). When the limit switch is triggered, clock *A* and *B* are stopped (as a stopwatch

is stopped), after which these watches can be moved so that their readings can be compared by some researcher.

From the point of view of observer *A* watch *B* move towards stationary clock *A* (Fig. 3). In the figure, observer *A* is indicated by a square.

Fig. 3. Clock movement *B* relative to the stationary clock *A*.

Question 1. Calculate how much time watch *B* will show when it stops when meeting with watch *A*, if when meeting, watch *A* will show 100 seconds (“00:01:40,000”)? It is prohibited to introduce additional bodies, clocks or reference systems. The answer to this question must be found using SRT formulas indicating the source (preferably Einstein's works).

Clue

According to SRT [1, p.19 ; 2, p. 22] the answer can be found using the formula

$$\text{Time } B = \text{Time } A \times \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\text{Speed}}{\text{Speed of light}}\right)^2} \text{ seconds,}$$

where "Time *A*" and "Time *B*" are the time of clock *A* and *In*, respectively, at the meeting.

At a speed of 0.866 times the speed of light, this formula looks like

$$\text{Time } B = 0,5 \times \text{Time } A.$$

Solution 1. A simple verbal calculation using the above formula gives the answer: clock *B* stopped when meeting clock *A* will show 50 seconds. Let's remember this result: clock reading *A* – 100 seconds, hours *B* – 50 seconds.

Question 2.

Let us now consider this same situation from the other side. From the point of view of observer *B* watch *A* moving towards stationary clock *B* (Fig. 4). In the figure, observer *B* is indicated by a square.

Fig. 4. Movement of clock *A* relative to the stationary clock *B*.

What time will clock *B* show? at the moment of stopping when meeting with clock *A*, if at the meeting clock *A* will show 100 seconds?

Clue

In this case, you need to use a similar formula

$$\text{Time } A = \text{Time } B \times \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\text{Speed}}{\text{Speed of light}}\right)^2} = 0,5 \times \text{Time } B, \text{ seconds,}$$

where

$$\text{Time } B = 2 \times \text{Time } A, \text{ seconds.}$$

Solution 2. An elementary calculation using the above formula gives the answer: clock *B* stopped when it met clock *A* will show 200 seconds. Let us also remember this result: clock reading *A* – 100 seconds, hours *B* – 200 seconds.

Question 3.

After clock *A* stops and *B* at the moment of their meeting (Fig. 2), these watches were transferred to some researcher to compare their readings.

What readings from this watch will the researcher record?

Solution 3.

Let us recall the results obtained above in answering questions 1 and 2. The reading of clock *A* according to the condition of the problem was equal to 100 seconds.

However, the readings of the same clock *B* when calculated in two different ways, they are strikingly different from each other. The first calculation method gave a value of 50 seconds, and the second method - 200 seconds.

This is as if one way of calculating the height of the Eiffel Tower from its shadow gave a value of 100 meters, and the second - 400 meters. A tower cannot have two heights at the same time.

B stopped at the meeting ? will they really?

In this example, the readings of clock *B*, calculated in different ways, differ from each other by “only” 4 times. However, if the speed of movement of the clocks towards each other is taken equal to 0.9999 (4 nines after the decimal point) of the speed of light, then the reading of clock *B* when calculated by the first method will be equal to 1.41 seconds, when calculated by the second method - 7,071 seconds. At this speed, the readings of the same clock *B*, calculated in two different ways, differ from each other by 5,000 (five thousand) times! At a speed of 0.9999999 (7 decimal points) of the speed of light, the time values of these clocks differ by 5,000,000 (five million) times.

What could be said about the formulas for calculating the height of the Eiffel Tower if, when calculated in different ways with the same initial data, they led to values that differed from each other millions of times?!!

Discussion of solutions

When solving the problem of the readings of the same clock, we have a contradiction. Clock *A*, when meeting according to the conditions of the task at the moment of stopping, will show 100 seconds. However, watch *B* will show, on the one hand, 50 seconds, and on the other hand, 200 seconds. This is impossible. Clock *B* stopped during a meeting cannot show two times at the same time. Stopped clock *B* can show one and only one time value.

"The relativity of simultaneity" cannot help

The question arises: can the concept of "relativity of simultaneity" help explain the contradiction that has arisen? According to the principle of "relativity of simultaneity", if two events separated in space are observed simultaneously in a reference frame "moving" with speed, then they will be observed non-simultaneous relative to the "stationary" frame.

However, in SRT this concept is applicable only if there are two events separated in space. In our case, there is only one event: two clocks *A* and *B* meet nearby when moving relative to each other, and at the moment of approaching they stop. The clock stops only once. Therefore, the same stopped clock cannot have two readings at the same time.

That is why the relativity of simultaneity in this case does not help explain the contradiction that has arisen.

About the theory of aberration - the first alternative theory to SRT, which is confirmed experimentally

The theory of aberration is the first alternative theory to STR, which is confirmed by two experiments [3-7]. One of these experiments was carried out by a team of 100 scientists and engineers in St. Petersburg in 2022 [8, 9]. The scientific publication about this experiment, according to the "international register of achievements and records," received the title "Property of the Nation" [10-12]. In addition, the reliability of the Aberration Theory is confirmed by the results of another experiment conducted by scientists from the National Institute of Standards and Technology NIST in Boulder (USA), who observed the most accurate clocks on our planet for 14 years [13, 14].

The theory of aberration is most fully presented in the monograph [3].

A shortened presentation of the theory of aberration is presented in [6].

In addition, popular scientific versions of the theory of aberration have been published [4, 7].

Works devoted to the theory of aberration can be purchased at litres ¹, or found in Internet search engines using the keywords "Plyasovskikh, theory of aberration, alternative to SRT."

The list of scientific works in the Russian-speaking space can be found on the website <https://elibrary.ru> by typing in the search bar the name of the author "Plyasovskikh A P" and the keywords "theory of aberration", "alternative to SRT", "aberration".

¹Books by Plyasovsky A.P. on the theory of aberration on liters: <https://www.litres.ru/author/ap-plyasovskih>

How the clock problem is actually solved

In accordance with the theory of aberration, the problem presented above can be solved in an elementary way. According to the theory of aberration, a clock has, firstly, a true rate, and secondly, an observed rate.

The true readings of the clock are observed by a stationary observer located next to the clock. The observed clock readings are recorded by an observer remote from the clock. The theory of aberration strictly proves that the true time of a clock is absolute. It does not depend on the movement of the clock relative to other bodies or clocks. The true passage of time of a moving clock is exactly the same as the true passage of a stationary clock.

That is why, if in the problem presented above the reading of one stopped clock is 100 seconds, then the reading of the other stopped clock will be exactly the same, no more and no less.

Conclusion

So, the article formulates a simple task that cannot be solved even by candidates and doctors of physical, mathematical and technical sciences. The highlight of the problem is that it should be solved using SRT methods, but when using STR, contradictions arise that no one can explain.

At the same time, this problem can be easily solved using the theory of aberration - the first alternative theory to SRT, which has been confirmed experimentally. According to SRT, moving clocks run slower than stationary clocks. According to the theory of aberration, the true readings of a moving clock go neither faster nor slower, but in exactly the same way as the true readings of a stationary clock. It is necessary to distinguish the observed course of the clock from its true course. The observed course of a clock depends on its movement relative to the observer. The true time of a clock is absolute and does not depend on its movement.

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